

TEACHERS ABILITY DURING EFL LESSONS

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ABSTRACT: In this article, we discuss the abilities demonstrated by teachers in their teaching activities, their types, and the associated skills. Additionally, we explore "Auxiliary Forms of Education," which are considered relevant today for improving the quality of education, as well as their effectiveness in expanding students' knowledge and preparing them for independent learning.

KEYWORDS: ability, pedagogical ability, perceptive ability, didactic ability, organizational ability, constructive ability, communicative ability, cognitive ability, moral qualities, volitional qualities, emotional qualities.

An individual's ability is defined as a set of characteristics that enable them to master a specific activity successfully and perform it creatively. Every person is a unique individual whose distinct traits determine their aptitude for certain activities. Success in work or a particular field largely depends on one's abilities.

Thus, ability is a combination of individual traits formed in life, which indicate a person's capacity to perform a specific type of activity at a high level. Moreover, ability refers to a person's individual potential and opportunities, distinct from knowledge, which is the result of study. Ability is a feature of a person's psychological and physiological structure. It differs from skills and expertise.

Ability is regarded as a gift bestowed upon a person. For example, a capable teacher achieves better results than their colleagues under the same working conditions. In many discussions, we hear people say, "That teacher still knows a lot," even if the teacher has limited experience. This indicates that the teacher possesses several pedagogical abilities, observational skills, pedagogical tact, and strong interpersonal skills, which help them excel in teaching despite their lack of extensive experience.

To be successful in their profession, every teacher must have pedagogical mastery. A teacher with pedagogical mastery achieves significant results with minimal effort, introduces innovations through their work, and is always accompanied by creativity. Only those who are talented and capable of pedagogical work can attain pedagogical mastery. Ability emerges and develops through the process of activity. It differs from skills and proficiency, which result from practice and learning. The development of ability, however, requires talent and intelligence, which progress based on the anatomical and physiological characteristics of the human nervous system.

For effective pedagogical activity, every teacher must possess and continually develop the following abilities:

1. Cognitive Ability – This refers to abilities related to specific fields of study, such as mathematics, physics, literature, and others. Teachers with such abilities possess not only the

knowledge required for the course but also a broader understanding of the subject. They constantly observe and analyze discoveries in their field and may even innovate in pedagogy themselves.

2. Explanatory Ability – This is crucial and involves effectively delivering educational material in an understandable manner, clearly explaining a topic or issue, and fostering active, critical thinking in students. A teacher must be able to adapt, simplify, and convey complex or unclear material in a way that is accessible to students. A capable teacher considers the level of students' understanding, what they know, what they do not, and what they may have forgotten. Some teachers, especially less experienced ones, might assume certain material is straightforward and requires no further clarification, leaving some students confused. A skilled teacher places themselves in the students' position, recognizing that what seems clear to adults may be challenging for students.

3. Observational Ability – This involves understanding the inner world of students, comprehending their personalities, and observing their psychological capacities. Teachers with such abilities can detect even subtle changes in a student's emotional state based on small signs or external behaviors.

4. Speech Ability – This refers to the ability to clearly and precisely express emotions and thoughts through speech and gestures. It is vital for teachers to communicate effectively.

5. Organizational Ability – This includes, first, the ability to organize a group of students, motivate them to solve important tasks, and, second, effectively manage one's own work.

By possessing and enhancing these abilities daily, teachers can ensure their pedagogical work is both impactful and efficient.

1. The Ability to Earn Respect – This refers to the capacity to exert direct emotional and volitional influence on students and, as a result, gain their respect. Respect is not only achieved through this but also through the teacher's strong knowledge of their subject, kindness, politeness, and other qualities. This ability is closely tied to the teacher's personal attributes, particularly their volitional qualities (such as courage, resilience, decisiveness, and strictness) and their sense of responsibility for educating and nurturing students. Students do not favor teachers who demand harshly or instill fear. Teachers who establish proper relationships with children, form friendships, and build sincere interactions demonstrate a presence of pedagogical tact.

2. Communicative Ability – This involves effectively communicating with students, finding the best approach to engage them, and establishing purposeful and cooperative pedagogical interaction. It reflects the presence of pedagogical tact and the ability to create meaningful connections with students.

3. Developing Pedagogical Ability – Enhancing abilities specific to teachers as specialists is essential for creating opportunities to further enrich and refine their skills. Certain methods and approaches are highly effective in fostering pedagogical abilities, such as:

- Self-improvement
- Creative approaches to work
- Studying advanced practices

Following the "mentor-student" tradition

Actively participating in training programs

Engaging in scientific and practical conferences

Attending regular seminars

Carrying out independent practical exercises

A teacher must serve as a role model for students through qualities such as morality, politeness, pleasant manners, honesty, discipline, responsibility, teamwork, integrity, humility, diligence, adaptability, fairness, and conscientiousness.

In conclusion, it is worth emphasizing that a teacher's emotional qualities significantly impact students' thorough understanding of their subjects, adherence to institutional rules, and the development of essential moral values. A teacher's emotional attributes play a crucial role in fostering collaboration, achieving harmony, and striving toward common goals with students.

References:

1. J. Hattie. *Visible Learning: A Synthesis of Over 800 Meta-Analyses Relating to Achievement*. Routledge. 2008 – 378 p
2. D. Stephen. *The Skillful Teacher: On Technique, Trust, and Responsiveness in the Classroom*. 1990. – 213
3. В.Н. Ходжайев. *Umumiy pedagogika nazariyasi va amaliyoti*. Toshkent. 2017 -
4. 240 P.
5. Хайтова, Г. (2024). Linguistic opposition as a philosophical category . *Актуальные вопросы лингвистики и преподавания иностранных языков: достижения и инновации*, 1(1), 56–58. <https://doi.org/10.47689/TOPICAL-TILTFL-vol1-iss1-2024-pp56-58>
6. Хайтова, Г. . (2024). INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA "YAQIN-UZOQ" OPPOZITSIYASINING LINGVOKULTURALOGIK TADQIQI. *Наука и технология в современном мире*, 3(1), 15–17. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/zdift/article/view/26059>
7. Tovasharovna, K. G. (2023). The Origin of the Phonetical Opposition Theory in Linguistics. *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769)*, 1(10), 624-626.